

Ahmed Ali's *Twilight in Delhi*: A Polyphonic Novel

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Abstract

This paper explores diverse voices in Ali's "Twilight in Delhi" (1940) through Bakhtin's theory of dialogism (1994). Multiple voices coexist in the novel in different situations. This paper aims at investigating the situations where the voices are amalgamated. This paper also examines the effect of this fusion of voices on the socio-political atmosphere of Delhi. Close reading technique helped in retrieval of eighteen situations in the novel where voices are fused, and then the actions and reactions of the characters in the novel were qualitatively probed. The paper finds that multiple voices in the novel exist and enhance the effect of the authorial voice. The study will contribute to get an insight into the situation in India, and how the two groups impersonated as the English and the Indian showed verbally their reactions. It will also help future researchers to view the narrative from dialogic point of view.

Introduction

In the modern era, voice is not considered reliable and authentic if it is not expressed (Bakhtin, 1994, qtd by Robinson, 2011). A nation's voice is not heard until it gains the other nations' support and favor. In view of this, thinking democratically is the need of the hour (Wilhelm, 2000). Padamsee (2013) says that Ahmed Ali, a great contender of democracy, gives space to the local writers in his novels so as to magnify his observations about the degeneration of Delhi and the downfall of the Muslims. His novel mainly centers on the political and literary variations occurred in the lives of the characters both at personal and social levels. It represents the degeneration of Delhi and the deteriorating moral and political norms and their effects on the life of Muslims of India (Padamsee, 2013).

In this novel, Ali gives space to the eminent literary figures of his time. Bahader Shah Zafar (1775-1862), the last Mughal emperor, was a poet whose poetry revolves around the themes of immortality of life, grief, anguish, and his nostalgia for his country (Farooqi, 2007). His famous poetry is said to be composed during his imprisonment in Rangoon, Burma. Sheikh Muhammad Ibrahim Zauq was Bahader Shah Zafar's poetry teacher. He was a Poet Laureate in his court. He was awarded with the title, 'Khaqani-e-Hind' (1790). After the demise of Zauq (1790-1854), Mirza Asadullah Khan Ghalib (1797-1869) became the Poet Laureate. His poetry is all about romantic themes. He has colored his pen, from love to mysticism. He is more famous for writing Ghazal, a poem about love (Indian Express, 2009). Nawab Mirza Khan Dagh Dehlavi (1831-1905), another literary figure, was also a romantic poet. Iqbal, a national poet of Pakistan was said to be his partisan in the early stage of writing poetry, and Iqbal (1877-1938) had acknowledged his poetry, and composed a poem in his tribute (Iftekhar, 2012). Zaib-un-Nisa (1638-1702), the eldest child of Emperor Aurangzeb, was also a poet who wrote under the fictitious name of "Makhfi". She surpassed in poetical concourse called "Mushaira" (Bashir & Sherwani, 2019). One of the key poets of the 17th century is also Hafez-e Shiraz (1316-1390). Subjects of his Ghazals are comprised of beloved, faith, and revealing hypocrisy. He deals with love, wine and pubs, all giving delight and freedom from restriction, whether in tangible worldly relief or in the voice of the lover speaking of divine love (Shaida, 2014).

The social, political and cultural relapses are portrayed in different situations in the novel particularly, when Ali incorporates voices of these Persian and Urdu poets of the 17th century in the novel who manifest different norms of society of then era such as social revolution, communal harmony and the celebration of past glory. Alamgir Hashmi (1990) remarks that the *Twilight in Delhi* was a classic fiction in Asia; its author was recognized as the first Muslim novelist of any consequence. A great writer like E. M. Forster (1879-1970) liked it very much, and encouraged its publication. Thereafter, Ahmed Ali was considered a pioneer novelist of the group of Indian English Muslim Novelists. This important novel of the late forties is compared to Raja Rao's *Kantapuram* (1938) and K. A. Abbas's *Tomorrow is Ours* (1943). *Twilight in Delhi* is simple in plot-construction, epical in scope and structure and limited in characterization, but vast in meaning and appeal. It is observed, that the technique which Ahmed Ali uses in the novel 'is not only to be widely inclusive of details and everything

but also to depict life with complete and objective honesty to show things - as they really are'. (Prasad, 1982, p.6)

Previous literature investigated this novel from different perspectives. Askari (1998) considered *Twilight in Delhi* as the beginning of a new literature in Lucknow, the place in India known for literary and political activities. He opines that the novel was written to familiarize British with the life style of old Delhi, to understand Delhi's environment and to address a period of history and culture of Delhi. However, Yaqub (2018) added that *Twilight in Delhi* does not succeed to grasp the imagination of Indian Muslims and the Urdu speaking populace but achieves to fetch critical applause from 'the western writers as it showcases Delhi, shorn of its glory, on the verge of decay' (p.43). In this paper, the focus is on the voices by paying special attention to the fusion of the characters' worldviews with those of the Urdu poets and intellectuals from the dimension of polyphony.

Literature Review

This novel has been discussed in previous literature. Awan and Yahya (2016) argue that it arouses pity and awe regarding the deplorable situations and circumstances of Delhi, which according to Sharma (2016), had been a seat of values and scholarship. Several combats were brewed on its ground. So, it has seen both glory and disaster. Darlymple (2004) declares Delhi as a city with an incorrigible wit, an abode of jinns skins back the sheets of Delhi's centuries-old history, illuminating an astonishing collection of characters along the way - from eunuchs to progenies of great Moguls. Ahmed (2009) is of the view that *Twilight in Delhi* along with other fictions, despite socio-political issues, gave recognition and a new trend to Pakistani fiction by projecting the sociocultural changes taking place in Pakistani society.

The review of the studies shows as if the entire novel speaks of woes and hues of the Muslims in India. All these aspects of the novel are conveyed either directly or indirectly, through the homodiegetic and intradiegetic narrators; or most of the situations are corroborated through the incorporations of the local poets' ideas.

Methodology

Bakhtin's notion of polyphony is the theoretical framework of the study. This notion originated from his concept of dialogism, which is an exchange of ideas and thought to categorize the expressions (Parks, 1991). According to Bakhtin (1994), this way of interaction is on ordinary use of communication. Its usage in narratives establishes a reality of language use. Polyphony, a key concept of dialogism recognizes the tone of multiple voices. The meaning of polyphony in writing is to discover the manifestation of different ideas to build disparate understanding. It functions when unlike declarations are in encounter or the idea is referred to as a plurality of views (Zhongwen, 1997). In response to these ideas, he suggests that the individuals should be let free to flow out their inner selves with full mindfulness. By doing so, the characters' consciousness remains independent leading to a plurality of speeches. Roth (2009) argues that if the characters are not free from the bondage of the author's control, the ideas will not communicate the actual position to the readers. Such a fiction is one-sided, and is often considered as monologism. Parks (1991) further elaborates the idea of polyphony by associating it with a dialogic form of interaction which is a much bigger spectacle than simpler responses in a discourse which is structured in the novel pervading all human speeches and all connections and appearances of social life, all that has connotation and implication. In a nutshell, the idea becomes impeccable when it comes with another socially fabricated voice. It stands alone when other texts are not involved (Tyson, 2006). This notion is promoted in the narrative to contextualize Ali's expressions about the private and the civil issues of India. Thus, this paper reconnoiters the numerous views of the homegrown bards, and those of characters in order to project Ali's consciousness and worldview about the situations that prevailed in India in his time. Data were collected from the novel with the help of close reading technique, which is manual reading and tagging. 18 situations were found in the novel, and they provided the sample to be analyzed through Bakhtin's notion of polyphony to explore the varied voices in the novel. In a situation, when Asghar shows indifferent attitude to Huzoor Ali who expresses his despair saying that he might be in love one day and he expected that his sweetheart would take notice of him. Here Ali mixes the voice of Urdu poet Hafiz by quoting his verse that 'Love is created first in the heart of the beloved' juxtaposing the novelist's belief that 'love is created not made'. And in the next line the narrator's point of view is reflected in the following lines that whosoever falls in love is fated to suffer (Ali, 2007, p.25). Further, Asghar is shown worried and dejected because he has fallen in love with Bundoo's sister Bilqeece but miseries, grieves and sorrows have engulfed him. Ali, in the voice of Persian poet Hafiz that 'the night is dark, the waves rise mountains high such a storm is raging (p.32). Saadi is also quoted here to let the reader know how dejected Mir Nihal's family felt when his elder son was ill as 'He who makes my woes for me. My brooding over them would be a greater woe than those (p.129). Further, the situations are revealed through heterodiegetic narrative embodied in the text of *Twilight in Delhi*.

Discussion and Analysis

The story begins with Hafiz Sherazi's well-known quatrain, discussing the description of the roofs of the houses and motion picture of a home in Delhi. The poet visualizes how the waves are swelling above the hills, and the storm is getting violent which abash the movement of the passers-by on the coast of the sea (Ali, 2007, p.32).

Heterodiegetic narrator's description of the city that it is full of scrapheap foul-smelling ditches; and the way he aches for the destruction happened in its soil, and his lamentation over the failure of the Mughals, are reverberated by the poet, who compares his wails and cries with a storm or a gloomy night (ibid, p.3).

The very first chapter opens with the heterodiegetic narrator's dirges over the degeneration of Delhi mingling his voice with Bahader Shah, the poet king, who rebounds the narrator's thought about the plight of the city who thinks that it has neither been the prospect of any eyes nor the means of rest of any heart, but a place full of dust and dirt (Ali, 2007, p.5). On another occasion, Shah expresses his sad emotion when he is asked where he was from. He replied that he was the inhabitant of The East, on which he is ridiculed by the people. So he was compelled to tell that he was from Delhi, the city which used to be a jewel of the world, the place which made the fortune. In the following lines, the same expression is made by the narrator when he states that the heritage of his forefathers was destroyed time and again. The city of Delhi was built and "rebuilt, coved and desired but still it is alive". More than this, it has seen the fall of glorious kingdoms" (p.5). Here, the narrator's desires for the past glory of the Muslim era reverberate with poet king Shah's tribute to the city of Delhi. The two texts, author's voice and Shah's voice, are brought together to strengthen the effect on the reader.

In the next situation, the narrator's voice is heard through Asghar, filled with the pride of youth, who once was the bestower of favours. He was the loved one, and not the lover. Ali believes that it is "sweeter to be loved than to love, whereas to love is full of pains and grief" (Ali, 2007, p.24). Huzoor Ali was very fervent to him too, but Asghar was indifferent to him, and did not care for Huzoor if he burnt himself like a moth. However, he had realized the reality that sweetheart could never be compelled for love. Finally, when he lost all hope of winning his heart, he curses him that he might fall in love, and suffer like him. The narrator's words are resonated with Hafiz's lines that affection or love is generated first in the soul of the beloved (p.25). In this situation, the two voices, the narrator's voice and Hafiz's voice, are amalgamated to support the idea about love.

In the next situation, his curses come true when Asghar hears the gentle voice of Bilqeece calling her Chabeli to see who at the door was. The voice was so fascinated that his heart began to beat. Ali reveals his feelings on such occasion saying that "there are thieves who only steal the Kohl, a black powder used to darken edges of eyes. They robbed her of her goods, and now it is his turn to steal" (Ali, 2007, p.26). Now, life became a burden and a storm for Asghar (ibid, p.28) as he fell in love with Bilqeece. Rage and excitement went through him, which he expressed in Persian Hafiz's words that night is sad and stormy for him. He is in a very depressed state which can be known to other people (p.32). He curses his fate for having little hope of attainment of Bilqeece. In this distress, Asghar is taken by his friend to his sweetheart named Mushtari Bai, where the music turns him even unhappier, as it reminds him of his love. Here, Ali combines his voice with a well-known poet Dard, who reflects his woes and wails in the lines who state that the sores of love had hurt him so much that he was not able to see a ray of light in the bright night. He further pours out his emotions that the injuries of affection have made him wander in the night. The night is the time to rest, and escapes from all the worldly humdrum, but the engrossing love has kept me awake and restless and dull having no spark. The idea that worries me is that she did not come to see me in this situation (ibid, p.73). The Qawwals, old fashioned oriental school praising the Prophet in their verses, also replicate Asghar's plight who sing that 'her poisonous eyes have hit straight at the lover, and how painful and dexterous she is' (pp.50-51). Now, Asghar philosophized the physical beauty of a flower, the blossoms of which fascinate the nightingale. He considers the girl as wax light which lures the butterflies to burn their fluffs. Mushtari Bai, a prostitute where he used to go when he was in sad mood, was also in love with him, but she thought that he was an unattainable thing for her. She considers him as a 'will-o'-the-wisp'.

Mushtari Bai, Asghar's sweetheart, loves him. What she gets in return, are the empty words, and frustrations. However she thinks herself otherwise. She deems herself either a candle of the night singeing itself the whole night, or a temporary abode to stay in. She compares him to a fertile place in the desert. On the other hand, he is also covertly guilt-ridden as he does not love her in reality. Ali's woes and cries are voiced by Bahadr Shah Zafar whose words reflect Asghar's passions for Mushtari Bai about his love, as he sang that she once compelled her lips on his lips, her heart upon his thumping heart. But all his confidence and arrogance in her are crumpled and devastated. (Ali, 2007, p.76)

Not only duality of voices is found in noble passions but it is also seen in mystical scenes in the novel. In a hymn, two declarations are polyphonically melded to reproduce the spiritual courtesies. In the next scene, Mir Nihal is seen proximate to the vault a mystic figure, who was killed by the Monarch. He went there to console his soul. Ali places Mir Nihal at the point of Sarmad, who feels slain when Bhabban Jan, a prostitute and his darling, dies. His present condition is voiced by a man going into the dark night, who begged if a lamp could be put afire near his grave, but he took a deep sigh that the gust of wind would extinguish it. The Persian

Poet, Sarmad's famous verses also echo his sentiments at her demise as stated that he has lost belief in fairly a different way. He has gone astray for dreamy eyes. Right now, I have come to the holy place to gain my lost love (Ali, 2007, p.96). A similar wave of spirituality appears in Asghar at the *Meelad*, when he called the Prophet. He finished his prayers with Nisar Ahmad's wonderful vocal sound that his deepest bidding is to be seated upon the trees grown on her grave when the bird of her dust is freed from its cage (ibid, p.82).

However, in the opening lines of Part II, Ali feels disappointed over the gloomy atmosphere of Delhi. His desperateness is expressed in Ghalib's famous couplets that his dejection has made him so oblivious that he does not feel how the unforgiving minutes of life go without realizing whether it is twilight or dawn (Ali, 2007, pp.86-87). The poet exposes his state of anguish and wretchedness. Ali states his contemplations about the similar state of affairs in the opening pages of chapter one that traitorous games were played with Delhi (p.4).

In the next chapter, Ali exhibits great reverence for the local poets when Mir Nihal is put in a literary society in Delhi. Mir and Daagh were praised for their expressive and dialectal phraseology in the literary gathering which Mir Nihal visits. Here, Saeel, a famous Urdu poet is quoted to read Ali's mind. Here, in the dialogic collaboration, it is understood about Ali's favorite poet names through Mir Nihal who quotes Daagh, who says that fictitious name is Daagh who exists in the hearts of lovers (Ali, 2007, p.117). Saadi is also mentioned to voice for such gentle souls as he says that he who thinks about his woes, he will become gloomier than he is (p.129). Connecting this idea with Ali, the narrator takes the reader to the wedding ceremony of Asghar where women unexpectedly began to miss their husbands (p.132). Bahadar Shah Zafar, an unfortunate king of India is quoted to resonate these voices for India's slavery, who states that he is not a mournful melody so why the people should hear it. He is rather the yell of a troubled soul and the agony of a wrecked heart (p.133). On another occasion, Bahadur Shah Zafar (p.140) is quoted that he "will not be able to tell the story of grief as his heart is wounded with torments for Delhi which used to once a happy place to live in, peace adorns its path, the foreigners have ruined it mercilessly (p.140). The narrator's inmost sensations surge out when Gul Banoo's cries are heard as Ali says that 'he is not pleased with the way the Muslims are treated and suspected' (p.140). The Part III of the novel moves with Mir's views conveying this message that the problem is not with the world but with him, he is not able to seek pleasure, though it is charming and fine-looking. It might be the reason that they are not treated fairly (p.152). Thus, the novelist is using the plurality of voices in a planned manner to leave a lasting effect upon the readers.

During the marriage party of Asghar, women's reaction over the invention of the soap-case, the voice of the author is revealed when they began to spell jinx on the brown English. The voice of the teller of the event with Mir and Zauq can also be heard. Ali remarks that the residents of Delhi began to show dislike for their natal abode, as their language, getups and behaviors lost their meanings for them. Zauq's love for Delhi is articulated as 'there is nothing in his heart, Delhi for Zauq to live with, so he is to go to Hyderabad' (Ali, 2007, p.196).

Part IV of the narrative flinches with Zaibun with the woes and anguishes of the war of 1918. Ali mentions these similar settings (Ali, 2007, p.230). Flu had worn out the city and killed many people. The news of diseases and dirges mourned them all and sundry. This grief is reflected in Asghar's sadness at his wife's loss, which he pours out after burial place every day. Nisa's expression is articulated here with Ali's to support the view (p.231). The novelist illumines the circumstances. He wails over the crises of identity, and burden of hatred in Delhi. He states that agony and grief have brought him to this dormant state of life (p.237).

The subsequent chapter displays the author's fear of what affected the norms of Muslim life, in particular, the mixing of the youth in Delhi. He is of the opinion that loves for beauty and poetry does not remain any more as new ways of thinking have overwhelmed the old. The inner singing of the known poet shows vulgar tune as in the absence of his dear friend, the wine seems to him like blood. While addressing the wine bearer as 'Saqi', he feels as if his heart baked with the heat of angst like kebabs (p.240).

In a nutshell, articulation of different sounds with the tune of the author in varied situations makes the arguments divergent. The vocalization of multiple voices demonstrates that the novel is polyphonic as each of these voices has its own perspective, its own validity, and its own narrative weight within the novel (Bakhtin, 1994). Moreover, the author places his own narrative voice between the character and the narrator. The novel does not seem to be an entity of a single objective world, but a plurality of consciousnesses constituting a fully dialogical world-view that is fully known to the readers.

Conclusion

The paper instigated the situations in the novel where the authorial voice accorded to the indigenous expressions made by the poets and other literary figures of the time. The novel is a representative forum for voicing different social, psychological and cultural issues of the Muslims of India. Ali's novel is democratic and polyphonic because it integrates the voices into his own say. The paper revealed that the poets, novelists and intellectuals not only had their eyes over the heartrending end of the Mughal era but on the

romantic and idealistic aspects of life also. This paper also revealed the mystical elements in the novel by projecting Hafiz, Sarmad with Qawwalis 'a religious song' that also represent the Muslim community and their love for their spiritual norms, in the sub-continent. The paper also found out that the messages become more distinct and more vivid when different voices are combined as the issues about Delhi, the psychological and social problems of the main characters are fully understood to the reader integrated with the authors. Furthermore, the study also established the reality that the message arisen out of the polyphonies is that the natives, in particular the Muslims, averted the dilapidation of Delhi. However, the tone of the narrator is harsher than the other sounds. The paper also found out that dialogism is ideally suited perspective to explore the latent insights in the text. The concept of 'polyphony' has been vital to this analysis. The study has examined that different voices are subordinated to the voice of the author. Thus, in contrast to monologism, it identifies the multiplicity of perspectives and voices. Everything said by the heterodiegetic narrator or the character was responded to the statements of the contemporary poets and scholars in different situations in the novel. This style of language-use, according to Bakhtin (1994), in the novel precisely represents the author's viewpoint.

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